

CAREER PREFERENCE ATTRIBUTING FACTORS IN RELATION TO SKILLS PERFORMANCE OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The study was conducted to determine the relationships between career preference attributing factors in terms of personal – related and school related – factors to skills performance of 120 senior high school students in their field of specialization as to generic skills and employability skills. Researcher used descriptive research design wherein the respondents answer the instrument through technological advancement use of Google Form as the main tool. The significant findings of this study on career preference attributing factors of senior high school students in choosing their track in senior high school, it is observed that the personal – related factors as to personal interest attributes to a “great extent” in the respondents’ choice of their career specialization. It is at likewise observed in considering respondents’ self – efficacy, social and economic demands, in school facilities, teachers’ competencies and students’ services. However, parents and peer have a “moderate influence” on the career preference of the respondents. On the relationship between personal – related factors and generic competencies of Grade 11 students, most of the personal – related factors except peer influence and parents’ influence were significantly related to the development of values and attitudes, literacy and numeracy, communication skill and time management. All school – related factors were significantly related to respondents’ generic aspects except literacy and numeracy skill which is not related to school facilities. The employability skills of the respondents are significantly related to personal -related factors except parents and peer influence. Moreover, the school – related factors were found significantly related to employability skills except teachers’ competencies which is not related to business orientation management skill of the respondents. Since, the findings revealed significant and non – significant relationship among variables, it is concluded that for those variables with significant relationship, the null hypothesis stated in the study is not sustained while those without significant relationship the hypothesis is sustained.

Keywords: Career Preference, Personal – Related Factors, School – Related Factors, Skills Performance, Generic Aspects, Employability Skills